

INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT IN BUKHARIAN KHANATE (THE IDEAS OF AKHMAD DONISH)

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Abstract. This article examines the distinct roles of the intelligentsia and intellectuals in societal development. The intelligentsia functions as society's moral compass: lacking direct ties to production means, it represents universal human interests, deriving its values from collective well-being and acting as a "spiritual mentor" for modernization. In contrast, intellectuals are defined by their critical, innovative agency.

Key words: own intelligentsia, spiritual mentor, morality, ethics, duty, representatives of social interests, intellectual minority.

The understanding of intelligentsia and intellectuals come together, however the intelligentsia is not a monolithic entity within society. Each social group in society creates the conditions for the formation of its "own" intelligentsia. The more complex the social structure of a society, the more diverse its intelligentsia becomes, and the more pressing the problematic situation of that society becomes.

To begin with, the intellectual is not a single, homogenous group in society. Virtually any society characterized by political and ethnic pluralism, confessional diversity, and social heterogeneity can serve as an example of this.

Secondly, the intelligentsia is an integral element of any society oriented towards development. It acts as the soul of a society's culture, its spiritual mentor.

Thirdly, one can seek and find the specificity of a "national" intelligentsia, but it is hardly appropriate to declare this phenomenon an exclusively European one.

Fourthly, there is probably merit in seeking a distinction between the "intelligentsia" and "intellectuals". This search can be developed through the opposition of "morality vs. ethics" (moral' – ma'naviyat), "duty and conscience" (burch va vijdon). Although there are other grounds for such a division as well. The term "intellectual" (intellektual) entered the French vocabulary in the 1890s. An intellectual was defined by their degree of professionalism. They ensure the process of producing ideas and their implementation in the techniques and technologies of civilization. An intellectual is directly engaged in one of the spheres of the system of social production. They serve society and ensure its management.

Fifthly, the intelligentsia has no direct relation to the ownership of the means of production, which creates certain difficulties for it, and at times even the threat of becoming co-opted. Any form of co-option creates conditions for the transformation of the intelligentsia into its opposite. It loses its essence, its identity, its freedom. On the other hand, the lack of direct relation to the means of production makes the intelligentsia a representative of society's interests "as a whole".

Its value orientations derive from universal human values, and its behavior is the "daily and hourly bearing of a feat" (A.F. Losev) [6, p. 156] for the sake of universal human well-being.

In general, the intelligentsia is a specific resource for the modernization of society, its spiritual mentor, intellectual guide, an intellectual minority – but not an intellectual elite.

Who are intellectuals? Researchers of the 20th century provide over 60 meanings and definitions of the concept of the intelligentsia. We can examine some of them:

Intellectuals are those who live for their ideas and thoughts. They must rise above traditional frameworks. They use new methodologies to solve important social problems. They transform old values into new ones, create new ideas necessary for human society. They employ critique to solve social problems. They reject ideas based on metaphysics. Most intellectuals contrast freedom and social equality with religion and power.

To understand who intellectuals are, it is necessary to know their characteristics. The characteristics of intellectuals are: To create new ideas; To rise above widespread, commonly accepted traditions; To be connected to the prosperity of their society; Constant professional mental work, as opposed to physical labor; To criticize the existing social and political state of society; Not to belong to any specific social group or stratum; To create a new mode of action and a new political ideology; To think about society, politics, and culture; To be informed about political conflicts within society; To be a creator, innovator, and propagator of culture; To be knowledgeable about the intellectual sphere of their society; Symbolic representation of stratum and class interests; To be able to disregard common folk and unjust traditions and customs; To guide society along the path of genuine aspirations, as opposed to fanaticism and minimal desires; To express one's disagreement regarding an existing negative situation; To know and highlight fundamental societal problems; To show ways of solving problems; To predict the future path of society's development; To identify a social ailment and diagnose it.

Analyzing the ideas of intellectuals should be mentioned Ahmad Donish who is considered the father of modern Tajik literature. He succeeded in creating his school, gathering enlighteners of the Tajik people around him [2, p. 281].

Despite all historical limitations, Ahmad Donish nevertheless remains the most progressive figure of his era. His works vividly expressed the struggle of advanced progressive ideas against conservative, backward views, reflecting the ideological struggle of the working Tajiks against the feudal system.

His enlightenment ideas, despite their limitations, were undoubtedly new and progressive for that time, serving the progressive forces of society. Followers of Ahmad Donish, living under different historical conditions and developing his ideas, were able to overcome the limitations of his educational views, adopt positions of revolutionary democracy, and, after the Great October Socialist Revolution, join the ranks of active builders of the new society. In this, to some extent, lies the contribution of Ahmad Donish, the father of Bukharian enlightenment. This constitutes his historical significance.

The explicitly anti-feudal and anti-clerical views of Ahmad Donish, his hatred for exploiters and love for the working people, his hatred for ignorance and love for enlightenment – all this confirms that he was the founder of the enlightenment movement of the Tajik people in the 19th century.

"Ahmad Donish was the first and essentially the only scholar of his time who so sharply denounced the social order of the Bukhara Khanate, vividly exposed the worthlessness of the Emir's regime, the obtuseness of the Muslim clergy, and clearly depicted the poverty and suffering of the masses." [2, p. 283]

In conclusion, it should be noted that national intellectuals served the national state and the Tajik nation. Those intellectuals named above are precisely the ones who made a significant contribution to the development of Bukharian culture.

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